

Experimental study on the flow-induced vibrations of a circular cylinder with a rear flexibly-hinged splitter plate

J. C. Muñoz-Hervás,^{1,2} M. Lorite-Díez,^{2,3} J. Ruiz-Rus,^{1,2} and J. I. Jiménez-González^{1,2, a)}

¹⁾*Departamento de Ingeniería Mecánica y Minera, Universidad de Jaén, Spain*

²⁾*Andalusian Institute for Earth System Research, Universities of Granada, Jaén and Córdoba, Spain.*

³⁾*Departamento de Mecánica de Estructuras e Ingeniería Hidráulica, Universidad de Granada, Spain*

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The flow around a circular cylinder is a canonical configuration that may be encountered in many engineering applications, as for instance, civil engineering, architecture, or marine structures. In particular, when bluff bodies are slender and feature low mass-damping characteristics, they may undergo flow-induced vibrations which may result in severe structural fatigue and damage.

Here, we present an experimental study on the effect of flexibly-hinged splitter plates in the flow-induced vibrations (FIV) of a flexibly-mounted circular cylinder (of diameter D) subject to an uniform cross-flow of velocity u_∞ . The dynamic response and forcing of the low mass-damping system is characterized for plates of different lengths L_p and different values of the torsional stiffness of the hinge k_p .

Reductions of the dynamic response of more than 90% can be generally reached at the upper branch, especially when a plate of length $l^* = L_p/D = 2$ with intermediate degree of torsional stiffness is attached, which is shown to represent the best solution as it mitigates the oscillations of the system (cylinder and plate) for the whole range investigated of reduced velocity $U^* = u_\infty/f_n D = [3.9, 9.8]$, where f_n is the natural frequency of oscillation. In general, the hinged plates are able to attenuate the vortex-induced vibration system response by increasing shedding frequency, until the ratio $f^* = f/f_n > 1$ is reached. At high values of U^* , a general transition to galloping-like dynamics, characterized by $f^* < 1$, occurs. The tested hinged plates modify the transition between regimes, which is associated to shifts in the phase difference between the forcing and response, combining features of the dynamics of both flexible and static rigid plates already reported in the literature.

The use of hinged plates has been proven to provide with a significant attenuation of the system response and its associated drag, a feature that can be considered of practical relevance in many engineering applications. In addition, the key aspects for designing these elements as the torsional stiffness and plate length have been analysed here.

I. INTRODUCTION

The flow around a circular cylinder in low mass-damping systems may produce flow-induced vibrations (FIV)^{1,2}. That configuration is a simple representation of many engineering applications where a structure is submerged in water or air flows.

In the case of the circular cylinder, this vibrating dynamics may be induced by vortex shedding that leads to vortex-induced vibrations (VIV). That particular response is characterized by a self-limited oscillation, guided by the synchronization between the vortex shedding in the wake of the cylinder and the natural frequency of the system^{3,4}.

^{a)}jignacio@ujaen.es

20 The periodic vibration of slender parts may result in structural fatigue damage and,
 21 consequently, control of FIV has attracted traditionally the scientific interest, which has
 22 given rise to a large amount of work devoted to FIV characterization and control^{3,5-7}.
 23 Within the literature on the subject of mitigating VIV, various passive techniques have
 24 been suggested. These techniques encompass solutions such as helical strakes, control rods,
 25 wire meshes, fairings, and splitter plates, among others^{5,8}.

26 While most of these systems are capable of suppressing efficiently the FIV, configurations
 27 such as fairing or rear plates, which renders the structure elongated and asymmetric with
 28 respect to relative misaligned flow conditions, may result into enhanced vibrations of in-
 29 creasing amplitude with the flow velocity^{9,10}. In particular, this dynamics is characteristic
 30 of unstable galloping-like responses, which are generally linked to a synchronized excitation
 31 with the cross-flow force and a slower dynamics due to added mass effects¹¹.

32 Rigid splitter plates, attached to the rear of the cylinder, have been traditionally proposed
 33 as efficient control devices to reduce flow excitation and decrease the drag acting on static
 34 cylinders⁸. As shown by Apelt, West, and Szewczyk¹², long plates may help reducing
 35 interaction between shear layers from both sides of the cylinder, affecting the shedding
 36 process and the aspect ratio of the separated recirculating region.

37 For freely oscillating cylinders, the use of rear plates can be however counterproductive
 38 when the relative stiffness is low. This occurs for large values of the reduced velocity,
 39 which is defined as $U^* = u_\infty / f_n D$, where u_∞ is the incident flow velocity, while f_n and D
 40 are the natural oscillation frequency of the cylinder and its diameter, respectively. Thus,
 41 as shown by Assi and Bearman¹³, short plates with length $l^* \leq D$ can already trigger
 42 galloping-like responses of systems with low mass ratio $m^* = m_s / m_f \simeq 2$ (with m_s and m_f
 43 being respectively the structure and fluid mass). In that work, flow visualizations indicated
 44 that due to the shear layer reattachment onto the splitter plate, the excitation is fostered.
 45 The influence of the shedding on the galloping-like response was already highlighted by
 46 Stappenbelt¹⁴, who also found that cylinder mounting long plates with $l \geq 4D$ do not show
 47 enhanced vibrations.

48 Similar results have been recently retrieved numerically and experimentally by Zeng
 49 *et al.*¹⁵, for different lengths of splitter plate and a cylinder-plate system with large mass
 50 ratio of $m^* = 50$. The threshold for the stabilization of the galloping response is, however,
 51 Reynolds dependent, as shown therein and in Sahu *et al.*¹⁶.

52 On the contrary, when flexible plates are considered, the system presents the ability to
 53 adapt its relative position with respect to the incident flow, what may help decreasing the
 54 amplitude response over a wide range of small and moderate values of the reduced velocity,
 55 as shown by Cui and Feng¹⁷ and Cui, Feng, and Hu¹⁸. In particular, the adaptive dynamics
 56 of the flexible plates prevents the interaction between the upper and lower shear layers,
 57 reducing the excitation. However, if secondary modes of vibrations of plates are activated,
 58 what may occurs at large reduced velocities, the cylinder's response can be amplified and
 59 galloping-like responses are triggered, as reported e.g. experimentally and numerically by
 60 Liang *et al.*¹⁹ and Sahu, Furquan, and Mittal²⁰.

61 The previous results demonstrate that the introduction of additional degrees of freedom
 62 (dof) to the vibrating system may help attenuating the FIV response in comparison to rigid
 63 plates.

64 In that sense, alternative configurations of lower mechanical order, such as multi-body
 65 solutions, can be also adapted. For instance, the additional degrees of freedom can be
 66 achieved by allowing rotary oscillations of the splitter plate or the cylinder-plate system
 67 around the pivoting axis^{21,22}, or by mounting the plate with a hinge at the rear attachment
 68 point²³. The own dynamics and rotation of the rear plates alter considerably the shedding
 69 process, and may reduce the amplitude of the oscillating lift acting on the body, as reported
 70 by Gu *et al.*²⁴ for the static cylinder.

71 The use of free-to-rotate plates as a control device of VIV was experimentally explored
 72 by Assi, Bearman, and Kitney²⁵ and Assi, Bearman, and Tognarelli²⁶. In particular, Assi,
 73 Bearman, and Kitney²⁵ showed that the rotary plate may reduce the FIV response when
 74 compared to the plain cylinder, as long as enough torsional resistance is set for the pivoting

75 point.

76 Besides, the use of flexibly-hinged plates, like those investigated by Shukla, Govardhan,
 77 and Arakeri²³ for the static cylinder, has not been yet analyzed in FIV applications of
 78 cylinders. Thus, to the best of the authors' knowledge, the only study dealing with such
 79 configuration is the numerical work by Wu, Shu, and Zhao²⁷, which examine the problem
 80 for a fixed laminar Reynolds number of $Re = 150$, and using a plate length of $0.5D$.
 81 This arrangement is shown to reduce the VIV oscillations for low values of U^* , but displays
 82 unstable galloping-like responses at large values of U^* , in a similar manner to the rigid plate
 83 of same length. The enhanced vibrations are shown to be associated to the reattachment
 84 of the shear layers at the plate tip. However, this behavior cannot be generalized to higher
 85 Reynolds numbers and longer plates. Thus, considering that such an arrangement has
 86 attracted less attention of researchers, the control effect of hinged plates, designed with
 87 a flexible torsional joint, on low mass-damping systems, in this case a circular cylinder,
 88 subjected to flow induced vibrations at moderate Reynolds numbers, is not clear.

89 In that regard, we study experimentally the effect of flexibly-hinged plates of different
 90 lengths and different torsional stiffness on the dynamic response of an elastically-mounted
 91 circular cylinder subject to turbulent cross-flow. The work aims to analyze the behavior of
 92 the system and compare it to those of flexible and rigid plates. The paper is organized as
 93 follows: the problem description and experimental details are introduced in Sect. II. Next,
 94 Sect. III is devoted to analyze the results on the dynamic response of the different cylinder-
 95 plate systems while Sect. IV shows flow visualizations of the near wake. The analysis of the
 96 force coefficients is presented in Sect. V. Finally, the main conclusions are drawn in Sect.
 97 VI.

98 II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

FIG. 1. (a) Experimental Set-up and (b) sketch of the problem.

99 Experiments were conducted in the Free Surface Water Channel at Universidad de Jaén
 100 (UJA). The water channel has a cross-section of $0.4 \times 0.5 \text{ m}^2$ and it is able to deliver over
 101 0.6 m/s . The velocity profile in the working section is characterised by a very low velocity
 102 variability, with a maximum deviation of 2%.

103 Figure 1 displays schematic representations of the experimental set-up of two-degrees of
 104 freedom. The first degree of freedom consists in an elastically-mounted rigid acrylic tube

105 that acts as a circular cylinder of diameter $D = 32$ mm, which can move in the transverse
 106 direction of the flow. The second consists in a rigid plate of length L_p and thickness $s = 3$
 107 mm ($s/D = 0.094$), which is flexibly hinged at the rear end of the main cylinder, and covers
 108 the whole cylinder length. The models were submerged 0.36 m yielding a length-to-diameter
 109 aspect ratio of $L/D = 11.25$. The assemble had an end-plate attached to his bottom end
 110 that prevented three-dimensional effects. Two springs were connected to the cylinder model
 111 providing restoring forces to the system, that hung from an air bearing rig that allowed the
 112 cylindrical model to oscillate in the cross-flow, y . Two PLA 3D printed parts acted as a
 113 support for the trailing cylinder, fixing it to the rig.

114 Additionally, the rigid acrylic plates were hinged at the rear of the cylinder by means of
 115 a flexible torsional joint modelled of silicone rubber, allowing the plates to perform angular
 116 oscillations, with a tip displacement y_p (see Fig. 1b). Thus, the cylinder-plate arrangement
 117 behaves as a a two-degrees-of-freedom system.

The structural parameters characterizing the problem are the mass ratio, m^* , and the structural damping, ξ . Considering the cylinder-plate assemble, the former is defined as

$$m^* = \frac{m_s}{\frac{1}{4}\rho_f\pi LD^2 + \rho LL_p s}, \quad (1)$$

118 where $m_s = m_c + m_p + m_a$ is the total mass of the system, given by the addition of that of
 119 cylinder m_c , plate m_p and a small additional mass of value m_a placed on the rig and used
 120 when needed to keep the value of $m^* = 11$ constant for all arrangements considered, i.e.
 121 isolated cylinder and cylinder-plates. Free-decay tests in air were performed to obtain the
 122 structural damping of the isolated cylinder and cylinder-plate systems, observing very small
 123 differences around the averaged value of $\xi = 0.0018$. Thus, considering the previously given
 124 value of m^* , the averaged combined mass-damping parameter was found to be $m^*\xi = 0.02$.

Besides, additional free decay tests in air of the rotary oscillations of the plates, while keeping static the main cylinder, allowed determination of their natural frequency, f_p . Subsequently, torsional stiffness of each flexible joint k_p can be estimated from

$$f_p = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k_p}{J_p}}, \quad (2)$$

125 where J_p is the polar moment of inertia of the plates, and considering the plates rotation as
 126 that of an 1 degree-of-freedom angular oscillator. The damping rate was also obtained from
 127 such decay tests of rotary damped oscillations, obtaining an averaged value of $\xi_p = 0.03$.

128 The Reynolds number based on the cylinder model diameter $Re = u_\infty D/\nu$, where u_∞ and
 129 ν are respectively the free-stream velocity and the water kinematic viscosity, ranged from
 130 approximately 3800 to 15200. The ratio between the free stream velocity in the channel
 131 and the average velocity of the cylinder (based on its natural frequency in water f_n) is
 132 defined as the reduced velocity $U^* = u_\infty/f_n D$, being the range covered in the experiments
 133 $U^* = [3.6, 9.8]$. The wake frequencies are made non-dimensional using the Strouhal number
 134 defined as $St = f_w D/u_\infty$, where f_w is the experimentally measured shedding frequency in
 135 the wake of the fixed circular cylinder.

136 Seven different control configurations have been tested, comprising three different plate
 137 lengths, $l^* = L_p/D = [1, 2, 3]$ or (l_1^*, l_2^*, l_3^*) , and four different torsional stiffness of the
 138 hinged-like junction, $k_p = [0.034, 0.096, 0.598, \infty]$ N · m/rad or $(k_{p1}, k_{p2}, k_{p3}, k_{p4})$, aside
 139 from the isolated plain cylinder. In particular, the stiffness of the flexible joint was varied
 140 using silicone rubbers of different shore hardness, allowing to study the following values of
 141 k_p for the parametric analysis. The $k_p \rightarrow \infty$ case represents the rigid limit, obtained by
 142 rigidly fixing and gluing the plate to the cylinder. Note that this variable can be expressed
 143 in dimensionless form as $k_p^* = 2\pi k_p/\rho u_\infty^2 D^3$, which represents the ratio of joint torsional
 144 stiffness to a hydrodynamic stiffness, or as a reduced velocity $U_p^* = u_\infty/f_p D$, but these
 145 magnitudes vary with flow velocity.

146 The motion of the cylinder and the flexibly-hinged splitter plate is characterized by using
 147 respective non-intrusive precise optical laser displacement sensors Leuze ODSL-8/VC66-
 148 200-S12 (with a measurement range from 20 to 200 mm, with a resolution lower than 0.2

149 mm), placed in the experimental set-up as shown in Fig. 1. The first sensor captures the
 150 motion of the cylinder along the air bearing rig, $y^* = y/D$, while the second one measures
 151 the tip displacement of the tested plate, $y_p^* = y_p/D$, which is computed here relative to the
 152 cylinder motion, $y^* = y/D$.

Besides, the flow forces acting on the cylinder along the cross-flow, f_y , and in-line (drag),
 f_x , directions were measured using a multi-axial precise load cell SRI-M3703A (with 50
 N range in x, y directions, with $< 0.5\%$ non-linearity and hysteresis and $< 2\%$ cross-talk
 effects). Thus, dimensionless force coefficients were obtained as

$$c_i = \frac{f_i}{0.5\rho u_\infty^2 DH}, \quad (3)$$

153 being c_x and c_y the drag and cross-flow or lift coefficients respectively, and H the sub-
 154 merged height of the cylinder. According to the load cell accuracy, these coefficients have
 155 an associated uncertainty of ± 0.001 .

156 All the previous measurements were performed with an acquisition frequency of $f_s = 1000$
 157 Hz sampling during at least 180 s, ensuring enough temporal resolution to capture the sys-
 158 tem dynamics properly. Considering that the minimum measured oscillation frequency in
 159 water was 1.3 Hz, at least 200 oscillation cycles were recorded for each test. Besides, to en-
 160 sure repeatability of results, 3 different runs were performed for each different configuration,
 161 observing very low dispersion ($< 1\%$ of the averaged value) in the obtained results.

162 Moreover, flow characterization was performed by means of PIV measurements to com-
 163 plement the understanding of the mechanisms behind the system dynamic response. In
 164 order to obtain the streamwise, u , and the transversal, v , velocity components, an horizon-
 165 tal laser sheet was produced with a 1.5 W Diode-Pumped Solid-State (DPSS) green laser
 166 (Novanta LAQ-GEM-532-1500) equipped with cylindrical and spherical lenses. The laser
 167 sheet was placed at mid height of the cylinder to illuminate the near wake region behind
 168 the moving arrangement (see Fig. 1a). The flow was seeded with $20 \mu\text{m}$ neutrally-buoyant
 169 polyamide particles and recorded with a Photron Fastcam SA 1.1, with a resolution 1024 px
 170 $\times 1024 \text{ px}$ up to 5400 fps, equipped with a 60 mm F/2.8 objective and a 532 nm filter. The
 171 recorded $1024 \text{ px} \times 1024 \text{ px}$ images were captured synchronized with the laser displacement
 172 sensors at 125 and 250 fps, depending on the flow velocity, to cover at least 20 shedding
 173 cycles. Also, the exposure time was modified for the different conditions to acquire im-
 174 ages of focused seeding particles. The recorded images were preprocessed making use of a
 175 specifically developed algorithm. Firstly, the solid moving parts were detected, obtaining
 176 a moving mask for the following PIV processing. Then, an improvement of the particle's
 177 intensity was achieved through a contrast enhancement process, which involved the sub-
 178 traction of a background reference image and the normalization of the image brightness²⁸.
 179 In order to obtain the velocity vectors through time-resolved particle image velocimetry
 180 (TR-PIV), we have used the Matlab toolbox PIVlab²⁹. The velocity vectors were obtained
 181 using interrogation windows of $48 \text{ px} \times 48 \text{ px}$ with a 50% overlapping, which resulted in a
 182 spatial resolution of 3 mm. Our field of view covers a region of view $119 \text{ mm} \times 119 \text{ mm}$
 183 with a scaling factor of 8 px/mm, which is enough to characterize the main flow features in
 184 the near wake. The temporal velocity in the wake at $(x^* = 3, y^* = 0.5)$ was also obtained
 185 using a Laser Doppler Velocimeter system (model MSE mini LDV), obtaining very similar
 186 results to PIV ones.

187 Finally, note that, in the following, any time-dependent variable will be denoted using
 188 lower case letters, e.g. b , while its temporal averaging will be expressed by means of capital
 189 letters, $B = \bar{b}$, unless otherwise stated. Note that, to evaluate the amplitude of the time-
 190 dependent variable as b , we will apply the Hilbert transform to obtain the instantaneous
 191 amplitude (envelope), \hat{b} , being \hat{B} its average.

192 III. DYNAMIC RESPONSE

193 In this section, we present the dynamic response of the different control plate arrange-
 194 ments investigated, as a function of the reduced velocity U^* (and Reynolds number Re),
 195 which are compared to that corresponding to the plain cylinder. Two different parametric
 196 studies are shown, namely: (a) the effect of varying control plate's length $l^* = L_p/D =$
 197 $[1, 2, 3]$ for a given torsional stiffness of the flexible joint $k_p = k_{p2} = 0.096 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}/\text{rad}$; and (b)
 198 the effect of varying torsional stiffness of the flexible joint $k_p = [0.034, 0.096, 0.598, \rightarrow \infty]$
 199 $\text{N}\cdot\text{m}/\text{rad}$, for a given length of control plate $l^* = 2$. The FIV dynamic response is char-
 200 acterized by the oscillation averaged amplitude \hat{A} and main frequency f , which are non-
 201 dimensionalized using respectively the main cylinder diameter, D , and the natural frequency
 202 of the cylinder system, f_n , to give $\hat{A}^* = \hat{A}/D$ and $f^* = f/f_n$.

203 A. Plain cylinder

204 The complete curves of amplitude and frequency responses with respect to reduced veloc-
 205 ity U^* , are depicted in Fig. 2(a1 and a2) for the plain cylinder. These curves are obtained
 206 by processing the temporal evolution of the cylinder y^* -displacement for each reduced ve-
 207 locity. The processing involves determining the averaged oscillation amplitude \hat{A}^* using
 208 the Hilbert transform and identifying the main frequency f^* of the vibration by means of
 209 analysis of Power Spectral Density function $\text{PSD}(f^*)$ (see Fig. 2b1 and b2 for the selected
 210 values of $U^* = 5.3$ and 9.0 .)

211 Thus, the uncontrolled case shows the classical amplitude and frequency curves for VIV
 212 of flexibly mounted cylinders in water, consisting of initial, upper and lower branches, being
 213 largest amplitudes reached within the upper branch ($\hat{A}^* \simeq 0.75$). The oscillation frequency,
 214 identified in Fig. 2(a2) with help of contours of Power Spectral Density $\text{PSD}(f^*)$, grows
 215 linearly as U^* is increased along the initial branch, following the Strouhal law ($St \simeq 0.18$,
 216 identified by LDV measurements), to reach a plateau within the upper branch, $5 < U^* < 6$,
 217 that defines the *lock-in* or synchronization range with $f^* \simeq 1$, where the amplitude is largest.
 218 From here on, the frequency rate f^* remains nearly constant along the lower branch, where
 219 the amplitude response decreases. These differences between upper and lower branches
 220 are easily observable in Fig. 2(b1 and b2), where individual time-sequences (note that
 221 $t^* = tu_\infty/D$) and corresponding PSD are plotted for two illustrative values of U^* .

222 B. Effect of the plates length

223 Let us now focus on the controlled cylinder-plate system, whose dynamic response is
 224 considerably different to the baseline case, as it will be next discussed. We first depict
 225 in Fig. 3(a1 and a2), results when plate's length is varied for a given constant value of
 226 the torsional stiffness. Thus, the amplitudes \hat{A}^* and main frequency ratio f^* are shown
 227 as a function of reduced velocity U^* , for the different lengths $l^* = [1, 2, 3]$ of the hinged
 228 plate. The response of the isolated cylinder is also shown as reference case. In general,
 229 the amplitudes are markedly reduced in the upper and lower branches when the plates are
 230 mounted, and little trace of response branches remains. However, differences are encoun-
 231 tered when the plate's length changes. In particular, the use of a plate of $l^* = 2$ attenuates
 232 the dynamic response of the system for the whole range of U^* investigated. Reductions
 233 in the amplitude of nearly 95% are reported for the upper branch, with its maximum at
 234 $U^* = 6.6$. However, for plates with $l^* = 1$ and $l^* = 3$, the picture differs and, in spite of
 235 providing general reductions of the vibrating response, a linear increase of \hat{A}^* is observed
 236 for the lower branch, so that amplified vibrations can be expected beyond the range of U^*
 237 studied here. This may be an indication of galloping-like behaviour, where oscillations are
 238 not self-limited, as reported in classical problems of FIV of cylinders with static splitter

FIG. 2. Dynamic response for the plain cylinder case: (a1) amplitude response \hat{A}^* and (a2) frequency response f^* versus reduced velocity U^* ; (b) temporal amplitude response $y^*(t^*)$ (where $t^* = tu_\infty/D$) with its mean amplitude (dashed line) and corresponding Power Spectral Density function, PSD(f^*) for the selected values of reduced velocity $U^* = 5.3$ (b1) and 9.0 (b2) (red points a1). In (a2) dominant frequencies are identified using circles representing maximum amplitudes in the contours of the PSD(f^*), while dashed line represents the Strouhal law given by $f^* = St \cdot U^*$, ($St \simeq 0.18$) and $f^* = 1$ is included by a solid line.

FIG. 3. (a1) Amplitude and (a2) frequency responses of the controlled system of cylinder with plates of different lengths $l^* = [1, 2, 3]$ for an intermediate value of joint stiffness $k_p = 0.096 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}/\text{rad}$, and (b1) corresponding tip amplitude and (b2) frequency responses of the relative displacement of mounted plates with respect to the cylinder.

239 plates (see e.g. Stappenbelt¹⁴). Interestingly, the shortest plate shows also an intensified
 240 response at low U^* .

241 The frequency response is also modified with the addition of plates, as shown in Fig. 3(a2).
 242 In particular, $l^* = 1$ and 3 show similar responses characterized by the initial vibration at
 243 frequencies slightly lying above the Strouhal line $f^* > St \cdot U^*$ and close to unity. This
 244 is especially clear for the shortest plate, where the vibration frequency is locked near the
 245 natural frequency, what may explain the amplified amplitude response at low U^* . As U^*
 246 increases above 5, the oscillation frequency displays a lock-in range with $f^* < 1$ for both

247 configurations, which is a typical feature of galloping-like responses.

248 For $l^* = 2$, the frequency response follows the Strouhal law initially, while the oscillations
 249 are discernible in the amplitude response (Fig. 3a1). However, after $U^* \simeq 6.5$ no coherent
 250 pattern is observed as the vibration is inhibited.

251 These types of response are somehow similar to previously reported results in the litera-
 252 ture for FIV of cylinders with rear rigid splitter plates. For instance, Assi and Bearman¹³
 253 studied the effect of placing a free-to-rotate splitter plate of $l^* = 1$, observing a similar
 254 increase of the amplitude response at low U^* , governed with frequencies close $f^* = 1$ and
 255 above the Strouhal law; while galloping is reported at large reduced velocity. The galloping
 256 type response reported here for higher values of U^* is however noticeably weaker in terms of
 257 amplitude, what might stem from the slight adaptation of plate to flow, as it presents mild
 258 oscillations on account of the finite stiffness of the torsional joint. Note that Assi, Bearman,
 259 and Kitney²⁵ reported mitigated responses when a certain degree of torsional resistance is
 260 set to the rotation point of the plate. Besides, the decrease of the frequency response for
 261 $U^* > 5$ may be related to a higher added mass produced by the addition of large plates that
 262 displace larger amount of fluid³⁰; we shall discuss this issue later when forces are presented.
 263 In fact, this effect seems to be exclusively related to added mass, as the mass ratio m^* has
 264 been kept constant for all experiments (using additional mass when required) and is not
 265 affected by the addition of longer plates.

266 To further elucidate the nature of the tested system oscillations, we present in Fig. 3(b1
 267 and b2) the relative tip transverse amplitude and frequency responses of the mounted
 268 plates around the pivoting point at the rear of the cylinder. Thus, it is observed that
 269 the relative amplitude \hat{A}_p^* grows in general with l^* , with the shorter plates showing weak
 270 relative oscillations, which are stronger at lower values of the reduced velocity U^* (i.e. where
 271 the relative stiffness of the hinge is larger). However for $l^* = 3$ a seemingly unstable response
 272 characterized by an increasing amplitude A_p^* with growing U^* is displayed. This dynamic
 273 of the plate may promote the stronger excitation of the cylinder depicted in Fig. 3(a1).
 274 Besides, as observed in Fig. 3(b2), the $l^* = 2$ plate mainly oscillates following the vortex
 275 shedding frequency given by the Strouhal law (depicted using a dashed line), while the
 276 shorter and longer plates follow this law initially, to subsequently start vibrating at a rate
 277 $f_p^* < 1$ at large U^* , which is also shown to guide the cylinder-plate system vibrations for
 278 such reduced velocities. The frequency jumps observed in Fig. 3 (b1 and especially b2)
 279 are caused by the quasi-periodic nature of the system response for the l_1^* and, especially
 280 l_3^* plates. At certain reduced velocities, the $f^* \simeq 1$ and $f^* \simeq 0.5$ frequency peaks have
 281 similar amplitude that provokes the observed frequency jumps. However, neither bistable
 282 nor hysteretic behaviours have been observed at the whole range of tested U^* .

283 These trends and magnitudes are somewhat similar to those reported by Cui, Feng, and
 284 Hu¹⁸ for flexible foils installed at the rear of a flexibly-mounted cylinder. This is however
 285 different from what was reported by Shukla, Govardhan, and Arakeri²³ for hinged plates
 286 behind static cylinder, whereby shorter plates display larger amplitudes, highlighting again
 287 the specific dynamic nature of the combined two-degrees-of-freedom system of cylinder and
 288 plate.

289 The coupled dynamics is further analyzed in terms of the flapping process of plates of
 290 different lengths and its phase with respect to the cylinder's vibration. The flapping of
 291 plates is illustrated, for selected reduced velocity at upper ($U^* = 5.3$) and lower ($U^* = 9.0$)
 292 branches, with help of Fig. 4(a), where the range of the cylinder's motion and the plate's
 293 relative angular displacement are shown with help of selected snapshots. The time history of
 294 the linear displacement of cylinder y^* and plate's tip y_p^* , along with their corresponding PSD
 295 and phase portraits (y_p^*, y^*) are depicted respectively in Fig. 4(b), (c) and (d). The flapping
 296 sketches in (a) and time histories in (b) show the progressive increase of the vibrating
 297 amplitude with growing length l^* , for both selected values of U^* , as already illustrated in
 298 Fig. 3. Besides, different coupled dynamics between cylinder and plate is observed in terms
 299 of frequency and phase for different lengths. For instance, the vibration of the shortest
 300 plate $l^* = 1$ is in general weak (Fig. 4b1,b4), since the plate is shorter than the vortex
 301 formation length for these kind of flows, as it will be shown in Sect. IV. Its vibration occurs

FIG. 4. (a) Sketches of the flapping process of the hinged plates and cylinder motion, (b) time histories (note that $t^* = tu_\infty/D$) of the flapping displacement of the hinged plate tip y_p^* (coloured solid lines) and the cylinder displacement y^* (black solid lines), (c) power spectral density of the plate and cylinder oscillations; and (d) corresponding phase portraits $y_p^* - y^*$, for $l^* = 1, 2$ and 3 . The selected cases and reduced velocity are $U^* = 5.3$ (1-3) and $U^* = 9.0$ (4-6), for plate's length $l^* = 1$ (1,4), 2 (2,5) and 3 (3,6). Note that in (d) x -axis and y -axis marks are identical for each phase portrait. The Strouhal value for each corresponding reduced velocity has been included in (c) by black dashed lines.

302 approximately at the same frequency and seemingly in phase with the oscillation of the
 303 cylinder, as displayed in Fig. 4(c1,c4). More precisely, at $U^* = 5.3$, the dynamics of the
 304 system is characterized by two frequencies in the PSD (Fig. 4c1), whose peaks correspond
 305 to a galloping-like frequency $f^* < 1$ and the natural frequency of the system $f^* = 1$.
 306 The concurrence of multiple frequencies and some lag between attenuated signals lead to
 307 the irregular phase portrait displayed in Fig. 4(d1). However, for $U^* = 9.0$, the cylinder
 308 vibration is periodic and enhanced, which is presumably due to an added mass effect, as
 309 inferred from the dominant frequency in the PSD is $f^* < 1$.

310 Thus, the phase portrait in Fig. 4(d4) displays a sort of elongated quasi-periodic orbits
 311 with some meandering, due to the concomitant periodic oscillations of the cylinder and the
 312 mild quasi-periodic dynamics of the plate.

313 For $l^* = 2$, the plate vibration is slightly amplified with respect to the previous case, but
 314 the general dynamics is considerably attenuated. The plate is shown to vibrate unfairly
 315 (Fig. 4b2, b5) following the vortex shedding (Fig. 3a2, b2), and therefore the frequency rate
 316 is $f^* < 1$ for $U^* = 5.3$, whereas for $U^* = 9.0$ the dominant frequency is $f^* > 1$, as displayed
 317 in Fig. 4(c2, c5). As discussed earlier, the VIV of the cylinder is nearly suppressed for both
 318 values of the reduced velocity. The lack of coherence in the phase lag between oscillations
 319 of the cylinder and plate (see Fig. 4b2, b5) may contribute, together with the globally
 320 attenuated vibration amplitude, to the definition of compact and seemingly irregular phase
 321 portraits (Fig. 4d2, d5).

322 Finally, the dynamics of the $l^* = 3$ system is clearly more periodic. As observed, the
 323 flapping features a periodic nature, and there is a good coupling between cylinder and
 324 plate vibrations, as illustrated in the PSD and phase portraits, which show closed orbits,

FIG. 5. (a1) Amplitude and (a2) frequency responses of the controlled system of cylinder with plates of different joint stiffness $k_p = [k_{p1}, k_{p2}, k_{p3}, k_{p4}] = [0.034, 0.096, 0.598, \infty] \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}/\text{rad}$ for length $l^* = 2$, and corresponding (b1) amplitude and (b2) frequency responses of the relative displacement of mounted plates with respect to the cylinder.

325 associated to nearly periodic dynamics. The slight meandering of the orbits is linked to
 326 the modulation of the plate's amplitude identified in Fig. 4(b3, b6). The vibration of the
 327 plate and cylinder follows the shedding frequency ($f^* = 1$) at $U^* = 5.3$ (Fig. 4c3), but it
 328 is guided by a lower frequency, $f^* < 1$, at $U^* = 9.0$, as occurred for the shortest plate. In
 329 spite of the amplified oscillations of the longest plate, the excitation of the cylinder is not
 330 as efficient, which may be due to the fact that the plate and cylinder vibrates out of phase,
 331 as depicted in the time series of Fig. 4(b3, b6).

332 These results show that there seems to be an highly effective length of $l^* = 2$, given a
 333 value of $k_p = 0.096 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}/\text{rad}$, for which the oscillations are suppressed within the range of
 334 reduced velocity herein analyzed. However, the role of the torsional stiffness of the joint
 335 still needs to be addressed, to check whether this magnitude affects the plate adaptation to
 336 the flow changes, and therefore to the vortex-induced vibrations of the cylinder.

337 C. Effect of the stiffness of the torsional joint

338 Figure 5 displays the effect of increasing torsional stiffness $k_p = [k_{p1}, k_{p2}, k_{p3}, k_{p4}] =$
 339 $[0.034, 0.096, 0.598, \infty] \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}/\text{rad}$ on the dynamic response of plates with $l^* = 2$. Note that
 340 the case of k_{p2} has been already discussed in the previous section since it corresponded to the
 341 case $l^* = 2$, and will be used as reference now. As illustrated in Fig. 5(a1), the amplitude
 342 response is in general weak, regardless of the value of k_p , although its value modify the
 343 nature of response. Thus, it seems that there is an optimal interval for intermediate values
 344 of the torsional stiffness, as the most flexible k_{p1} and rigid k_{p4} cases display less attenuated
 345 amplitudes.

346 The most flexible joint k_{p1} displays efficient suppression of the oscillations along the
 347 initial ($U^* \leq 5.1$) and upper ($5.1 < U^* < 6.1$) branches, although an increasing amplitude
 348 is observed for the reduced velocity range $6.1 < U^* < 9$, coincident with the interval of
 349 the original lower branch. At $U^* = 9$ the amplitude decays suddenly, to achieve complete
 350 suppression of the oscillations.

351 As observed in Fig. 5(a2), the frequency response follows approximately a linear trend,
 352 which lies however below that of the shedding frequency of the plain cylinder $St \cdot U^*$.
 353 This trend is maintained until $U^* = 9$, where $f^* \simeq 1$. From here on, the oscillations are
 354 attenuated and the frequency decreases. This coupled dynamics of the system is seemingly

FIG. 6. (a) Sketches of the flapping process of the hinged plates and the cylinder motion, (b) time histories (note that $t^* = tu_\infty/D$) of the flapping displacement of the hinged plate tip y_p^* (coloured solid lines) and the cylinder displacement y^* (black solid lines), (c) power spectral density of the plate and cylinder oscillations; and (d) corresponding phase portraits $y_p^* - y^*$, for $k_{p1} = 0.034\text{N} \cdot \text{m/rad}$, $k_{p3} = 0.598\text{N} \cdot \text{m/rad}$ and $k_{p4} \rightarrow \infty$. The selected cases and reduced velocity are $U^* = 5.3$ (1-3) and $U^* = 9.0$ (4-6), for torsional stiffness k_{p1} (1,4), k_{p3} (2,5) and k_{p4} (3,6). Note that in (d) x -axis and y -axis marks are identical for each phase portrait. The Strouhal value for each corresponding reduced velocity has been included in (c) by black dashed lines.

355 guided by the plate's oscillations, as shown by the relative amplitude \hat{A}_p^* shown in Fig. 5(b1).
 356 Note that the amplitude response of the plate is considerably larger as its maximum value
 357 equals $\hat{A}_p^* \simeq 0.7$, while $\hat{A}^* \simeq 0.2$.

358 Stappenbelt¹⁴ reported similar responses for short rigid splitter plates, where large am-
 359 plitude response ends at the end of the VIV lock-in range.

360 The increase of the torsional stiffness k_p weakens progressively the relative amplitude
 361 of the plate's oscillations, as shown in Fig. 5(b1). This attenuated dynamics alters the
 362 coupled dynamic response of the cylinder-plate system depicted in Fig. 5(a1). As observed,
 363 the weakest response is featured by k_{p2} , for which the oscillations are nearly nil over the
 364 whole range of U^* as already discussed in the previous Sect. III B.

365 On the other hand, the response for k_{p3} is also very weak, although slightly less attenuated
 366 than that corresponding to the reference k_{p2} case. In particular, the response is amplified at
 367 very low values of U^* when compared to the plain cylinder. This mild oscillation continues
 368 along the former initial branch, but it vanishes around $U^* \simeq 6$, from where the response
 369 practically disappears.

370 Interestingly, the system with the rigid splitter plate, i.e. $k_{p4} \rightarrow \infty$, displays also an
 371 overall attenuated response, although the oscillations of the system are amplified for small
 372 and large values of reduced velocity, thus defining two distinct regions of response.

373 When the frequency of the system is analyzed with help of Fig. 5(a2), it is observed
 374 that these two regions identified for large stiffness k_{p3} and k_{p4} are respectively related to
 375 similar frequency responses. In particular, at low U^* , the system oscillations are guided by
 376 a linearly increasing frequency ratio f^* , following approximately the shedding frequency. In
 377 general, this linear trend lies slightly below the shedding law of the plain cylinder $St \cdot U^*$,

FIG. 7. Mean tip displacement Y_p^* of the $l^* = 2$ plate for different torsional stiffness.

378 what may be due to the increased hydrodynamic inertia (with the transverse motions) of
 379 the cylinder-plate system. Additionally, at high U^* , the frequency response displays nearly
 380 constant ratios of $f^* \simeq 0.4$, what again might be an indication of beginning of galloping-
 381 like response, which is particularly evident in the case of $k_p \rightarrow \infty$, as the value of \hat{A}^*
 382 rises monotonously at large U^* . This behaviour mimics that reported in Assi, Bearman,
 383 and Kitney²⁵ for rigid splitter plates. For all the hinged $l^* = 2$ plates, the shear layers
 384 wrap around the plate alternatively, which provokes a new mechanism of flow excitation
 385 under these configurations. The different obtained responses depend on how the flow forcing
 386 is sunk by the different employed flexible joints, as will be discussed in Sects. IV and V.
 387 Finally, note that the plate's relative oscillations shown Fig. 5(b2), display similar frequency
 388 responses than that of the cylinder, especially for k_{p3} .

389 Again, the coupled dynamics is further analyzed in terms of the flapping process of
 390 plates of different torsional stiffness and its phase with respect to the cylinder's vibration.
 391 Thus, Fig. 6 displays the flapping of plates and the cylinder motion (a), time-series of
 392 cylinder y^* and plate's tip y_p^* displacement (b), corresponding PSD (c) and phase portraits
 393 (y_p^*, y^*) (d), for reduced velocity values of $U^* = 5.3$ (1-3) and $U^* = 9.0$ (4-6), and torsional
 394 stiffness $k_{p1} = 0.034\text{N} \cdot \text{m}/\text{rad}$, $k_{p3} = 0.598\text{N} \cdot \text{m}/\text{rad}$ and $k_{p4} \rightarrow \infty$. Note that case
 395 $k_{p2} = 0.092\text{N} \cdot \text{m}/\text{rad}$, is represented in Fig. 4, and denoted as $l^* = 2$.

396 First, as expected from the previous discussion on \hat{A}^* and \hat{A}_p^* , the lowest value of torsional
 397 stiffness k_{p1} displays the largest relative flapping amplitude (Fig. 6a1, b1), which grows with
 398 the reduced velocity. The cylinder's vibration is however less intense, and both oscillating
 399 histories of cylinder and plate are seen to be out-of-phase for both values of the reduced
 400 velocity $U^* = 5.3$ (Fig. 6b1, d1) and 9.0 (Fig. 6b4, d4). As inferred from Fig. 5, the
 401 dominating frequencies of both the plate and cylinder oscillations are the same, and increase
 402 with U^* . This fact leads to phase portraits which display close circular orbits characteristic
 403 from periodic or quasi-periodic dynamics (note that for $U^* = 9.0$, there is some modulation
 404 on the amplitude of the time-series, what translates into a stronger meandering of the
 405 orbits).

406 As the torsional stiffness increases, the flapping amplitude weakens, as illustrated in
 407 Fig. 6(a2, a5) and (b2, b5) for k_{p3} . It is observed that the cylinder and plate oscillates
 408 approximately in phase and with the same frequency (Fig. 6 c2, c5). As a consequence,
 409 the phase diagrams show traces developing approximately along the bisector diagonal. The
 410 irregularity of the portraits shape is the outcome of the erratic weak oscillating signals of
 411 the plate and cylinder, which is especially evident for $U^* = 9.0$. Finally, for the static
 412 rigid plate, i.e. $k_{p4} \rightarrow \infty$, the amplitude of plate's displacement is obviously close to
 413 zero in Fig. 6(a3, a6) and (b3, b6), being the weak, irregular vibration simply related
 414 to the experimental noise, as we are characterizing the motion of the plate with respect
 415 to the cylinder displacement. Consequently, the phase portrait display horizontal shapes
 416 associated to sole vibrations of the cylinder y^* (along the abscissa axis).

417 Finally, once the oscillating dynamics of the system has been discussed, let us analyzed

418 the mean position of the plates. As reported by Cimbalá and Garg²¹ for free-to-rotate
 419 cylinders with fixed splitter plates, or similarly, by Assi, Bearman, and Kitney²⁵ and Gu
 420 *et al.*²⁴ for free-to-rotate splitter plates mounted in cylinders, these multibody systems may
 421 perform rotary oscillation around asymmetric deflected positions that are the outcome of
 422 bi-stable equilibrium of the fluid-structure interaction coupling. In view of the similarities
 423 between those systems and that of the hinged plate presented here, we analyze, with help
 424 of Fig. 7, the evolution of the mean position of the $l^* = 2$ plate, given by the mean tip
 425 displacement, $Y_p^* = Y_p/D$, against U^* , for the three values of torsional stiffness k_p . It
 426 can be observed that the location of k_{p2} and k_{p3} are approximately centred, i.e. $Y_p^* \simeq 0$.
 427 Interestingly, the most flexible joint, k_{p1} , features also a centred location for $U^* \leq 9.0$,
 428 however, above that threshold, a divergence occurs and Y_p takes a constant value of 0.32
 429 hereinafter. Such asymmetric deflection of the most flexible plate leads to the complete
 430 attenuation of the oscillating dynamics, as shown in Fig. 5. The attenuation of the VIV
 431 response was also reported by Assi, Bearman, and Kitney²⁵ for a free-to-rotate plate. It was
 432 also shown by Gu *et al.*²⁴ that the asymmetric deflection of the plates entails the decrease
 433 in the fluctuating lift.

434 That said, the implementation of hinged splitter plates has been shown to lead to mit-
 435 igated or partially suppressed oscillations over a wide range of reduced velocity, with the
 436 cylinder responding differently depending on the length of the plate or the torsional stiffness
 437 of the flexible joint. This controlled dynamics will be subsequently analyzed based on the
 438 force coefficients and the phase difference between the forcing and the response, together
 439 with the flow visualization of the near wake for selected representative cases, which will also
 440 help shedding some light on the control mechanisms acting here.

441 IV. FLOW VISUALIZATIONS

442 Once the dynamic response of the system has been discussed, we present next the results
 443 from the flow visualizations undertaken for selected cases. The flow visualizations have
 444 been performed for those configurations which better explain the observed differences on
 445 the dynamic response. More precisely, the experiments have been performed for the fixed
 446 cylinder, the free-to-vibrate plain cylinder and two cylinder-plate arrangements with length
 447 $l^* = 2$, namely two different joint stiffness, k_{p2} and k_{p4} .

448 Figs.(8 - 11) present the shedding process by means of phase-averaged dimensionless
 449 spanwise vorticity contours (note that $w^* = wD/u_\infty$, where w is the spanwise vorticity)
 450 and flow streamlines at $U^* = 5.3$ ($Re \simeq 7000$). Eight selected phases, from 0 to $7\pi/4$, have
 451 been averaged using the cylinder subsequent positions during at least 20 shedding cycles.
 452 Here, the 0 phase corresponds to the instant where the cylinder position crosses from $y^* < 0$
 453 positions to $y^* > 0$ ones. For the case denoted as fixed cylinder, in which the cylinder is not
 454 allowed to move, the phases are obtained from the the transversal velocity (v^*) temporal
 455 evolution at ($x^* = 2.5$, $y^* = 0$), here also, the 0 phase corresponds to the instant where the
 456 transversal velocity goes from $v^* < 0$ values to $v^* > 0$ ones.

457 A. Flow around the plain cylinder

458 In this section, we compare the fixed circular cylinder wake dynamics with that of the
 459 free-to-vibrate plain cylinder. In the first case, the measured flow represents the canonical
 460 vortex shedding in the wake behind a fixed cylinder³¹. As it can be seen in Fig. 8, alternative
 461 vortices are formed and shed from each side of the cylinder at a given frequency, f_w . In the
 462 shedding sequence, it can be observed that the vortex formation length is around $x^* \simeq 2$,
 463 especially at 0 and $5\pi/4$ phases. This feature may be able to explain why the plate with a
 464 length $l^* = 2$ exhibits the best performance, as it alters the formation length.

465 On the other hand, the free-to-vibrate plain cylinder vortex shedding sequence is illus-
 466 trated in Fig. 9 at $U^* = 5.3$. This reduced velocity corresponds to the maximum cylinder

FIG. 8. Phase-averaged spanwise vorticity (w^*) contours and flow streamlines over one cycle of shedding for the fixed plain cylinder case at $Re \simeq 7000$. The corresponding phase-averaged positions of the cylinder have been plotted in different panels to better illustrate the shedding process.

FIG. 9. Phase-averaged spanwise vorticity (w^*) contours and flow streamlines over one cycle of shedding for the free-to-vibrate plain cylinder case at $U^* = 5.3$.

467 response on the upper branch. Figure 9 depicts that the cylinder displacement induces a
 468 greater rotation in the flow, forming stronger vortices (with higher associated vorticity) that
 469 may produce higher transverse forces. In addition, the core positions of the shed vortices
 470 are displaced far away from the cylinder center, reducing the importance of the recirculation
 471 region in this flow configuration.

472 B. Effect of the torsional joint stiffness on the near wake

473 Now, we focus on the interaction between the tested splitter plates and the forming wake.
 474 In order to analyze the role of the flexible silicone in the fluid-structure mechanisms, we have
 475 performed experiments for a fixed plate length $l^* = 2$ and two different joint stiffness, k_{p2}
 476 and k_{p4} . In the tested cylinder-plate arrangements, the separated shear layers wrap around
 477 the plate alternatively (see Figs. 10 and 11). However, for the rigid plate, k_{p4} , the wake
 478 excitation has to go directly to the cylinder (and to the springs on the low mass-damping
 479 system), causing a stronger cylinder's response. When we introduce the silicone rubber,
 480 the wake excitation can be absorbed by the torsional joint, reducing the magnitude of the
 481 forcing transferred to the cylinder. As mentioned above, it can be noticed that the control
 482 effect of the hinged plate is particularly important for this plate's length ($l^* = 2$) since the
 483 recirculation regions formed at each side of the plates have a $\simeq 2D$ extension (see Figs. 10
 484 and 11). In addition, the formation of a tip vortex can be observed for the rigid plate k_{p4}

485 (see Fig. 11) at $\pi/4$ or $3\pi/2$ phases, in contrast to the plate k_{p2} , where it cannot be noticed
 486 (see Fig. 10). This effect may be associated to the ability of the hinged plate to adapt to
 487 the flow, which contributes to reduce the wake forcing on the cylinder-plate system.

FIG. 10. Phase-averaged spanwise vorticity (w^*) contours and flow streamlines over one cycle of shedding for the k_{p2} cylinder-plate arrangement case at $U^* = 5.3$. Note that the corresponding phase-averaged positions of the cylinder and the plate have been included to better illustrate the shedding process.

488 Finally, Fig. 10 shows that the degree of freedom introduced with the flexibility of the
 489 torsional joint allows to reduce the transversal velocity on the wake in comparison with the
 490 rigid plate (see Fig. 11), which may in turn reduce the wake excitation. Following this idea,
 491 we can compute the integral wake transversal velocity, \tilde{v} , at a given streamwise position as,
 492 $\tilde{v}(t^*) = \langle v(y^*, t^*) \rangle$, where $\langle \rangle$ represents spatial averaging.

FIG. 11. Phase-averaged spanwise vorticity (w^*) contours and flow streamlines over one cycle of shedding for the k_{p4} cylinder-plate arrangement case at $U^* = 5.3$. Note that the corresponding phase-averaged positions of the cylinder and the plate have been included to better illustrate the shedding process.

493 This magnitude accounts for the instantaneous transversal velocity in the wake that
 494 may qualitatively measure the transversal wake forcing or excitation for a given near wake
 495 topology. Figure 12 represents the temporal evolution of \tilde{v} for the selected phases depicted
 496 in Figs.(8 - 11) at $x^* = 3.5$ between $-1.5 \leq y \leq 1.5$. As expected, the alternative periodic
 497 shedding of vortices of the fixed and free-to-vibrate plain cylinder cases induces a strong
 498 transversal velocity in the wake. that provokes the strong cylinder response. Conversely,
 499 the integral wake transversal velocity is reduced when a splitter plate is introduced, which
 500 may explain the observed reduction on the cylinder-plate response. A comparison between
 501 the results for k_{p2} and k_{p4} reveals that \tilde{v} is weaker as the stiffness is reduced. This fact may

502 be attributed to the damping action of the silicone rubber, which seems to reduce the wake
 503 excitation, strongly mitigating the cylinder's response, as previously seen in Sect. III.

FIG. 12. Integral wake transversal velocity, \tilde{v} , computed at $x^* = 3.5$ for $-1.5 \leq y \leq 1.5$ at selected phases of the shedding cycle corresponding to different configurations.

504 V. FORCE COEFFICIENTS

505 A. Cross-flow force coefficient and components

The analysis of the force coefficients is next addressed. The cross-flow or lift coefficient amplitude \hat{C}_y is computed as indicated in Sect. II. This coefficient can additionally divided into components in phase with the acceleration, $\hat{C}_{y,a}$, and with the velocity, $\hat{C}_{y,u}$, according to the expressions given in Jiménez-González and Huera-Huarte³²:

$$\hat{C}_{y,a} = \frac{\sqrt{2} (f_y - F_y)}{0.5\rho D L u_\infty^2} \frac{y}{\sqrt{Y^2}}, \quad (4)$$

and

$$\hat{C}_{y,u} = \frac{\sqrt{2} (f_y - F_y)}{0.5\rho D L u_\infty^2} \frac{\dot{y}}{\sqrt{Y^2}}, \quad (5)$$

506 where \dot{y} is the temporal derivative of the cross-flow displacement of the cylinder, y .

These components may help interpreting, respectively, the effect of inertia and transfer of energy between fluid and structure. In particular, the positive values of $C_{y,u}$ indicate a net transfer from the fluid to the body, what excites the structural response; while the sign of $C_{y,a}$ is related to the effective added mass and phase between forcing and response³. In fact, to complement the analysis, the averaged phase difference, Φ , between the y displacement and the lift force, c_y , was obtained using the Hilbert transform to the temporal variable,

$$\phi = \phi_{c_y} - \phi_y. \quad (6)$$

508

509 Figure 13 depicts the amplitude of lift coefficient and corresponding components, together
 510 with the phase difference, for the different plate length l^* based on stiffness $k_{p2} = 0.096$
 511 N·m/rad and the plain cylinder, which will be first analyzed to set a reference. For that case,
 512 the lift coefficient is shown to peak, with $\hat{C}_y \simeq 1.5$, approximately at $U^* \simeq 5.1$ (see Fig. 13a),
 513 that corresponds to the amplitude jump between initial and upper branches in Fig. 2(a).
 514 After that, there is a sudden decrease of \hat{C}_y coinciding with the transition between upper

FIG. 13. Amplitude of (a) lift coefficient, \hat{C}_y , along with corresponding components in phase with velocity (b) and displacement (c), and phase difference between lift and y -displacement (d), for different plate length l^* and stiffness $k_{p2} = 0.096$ N-m/rad. A solid line has been included for $\hat{C}_{y,a}$ to illustrate the effective added mass and phase between forcing and response.

515 and lower branches, from which the value decays mildly with growing U^* , until reaching
 516 a nearly nil value as the VIV response decays in amplitude. The lift components in phase
 517 with velocity, $\hat{C}_{y,u}$, presents positive values for all U^* , reaching its maximum within the
 518 upper branch of amplitude response at $U^* = 5.3$. As mentioned previously, this coefficient
 519 $\hat{C}_{y,u}$ can be used to estimate the fluid damping effect and the energy transferred from the
 520 fluid to the moving structure; so that its maximum absolute value is associated to largest
 521 excitation. Besides, the component $\hat{C}_{y,a}$ features a peak at $U^* \simeq 5.3$, and decreases until
 522 reaching a negative value for $U^* > 6.0$, where the phase changes from 0° to 180° (Fig. 13d).
 523 This phase shift takes place once the system oscillating frequency reaches its natural one,
 524 i.e. $f^* \simeq 1$ (Fig. 2a2), and entails the attenuation of the amplitude response over the lower
 525 branch, as now the exciting force acts in the opposite direction to the body's motion.

526 The effect of mounting a rear hinged plate modifies the excitation force, and trends of
 527 coefficients are considerably different. In particular, for the plate of length $l^* = 1$, the
 528 lift coefficient amplitude is large at low values of reduced velocity U^* , and decreases with
 529 it, to reach a minimum around $U^* \simeq 5$ where the original upper branch of the amplitude
 530 response corresponding to the plain cylinder emerges. From here on, the lift amplitude starts
 531 to grow again monotonously. A similar trend is found for the inertia component $\hat{C}_{y,a}$, which
 532 is greater than that of the plain cylinder for low and high values of reduced velocity. The
 533 higher values of $\hat{C}_{y,a}$ are consistent with higher added mass, and therefore, lower frequencies
 534 at high U^* ³. Additionally, the dynamic response of $l^* = 1$ exhibits very low values of $\hat{C}_{y,u}$,
 535 i.e. lower energy transfer, in contrast to the results of the plain cylinder (except for the
 536 lowest values of U^* investigated). As a result, the general dynamic response of the system
 537 cylinder-plate is attenuated, providing a weaker response (see Fig. 3). That said, unlike the
 538 plain cylinder, the phase difference between forcing and response does not change its value
 539 and is always 0° (Fig. 13d) over the whole range of reduced velocity investigated. This may
 540 compensate the lower energy transfer and foster the response at large reduced velocity.

541 Similar trends are obtained for the plate of $l^* = 3$, although the lift \hat{C}_y and correspond-

ing component $\hat{C}_{y,a}$ show a progressive decreasing amplitude at low U^* , as the length grows. It is interesting to observe that now the $\hat{C}_{y,a}$ component reaches negative values for $5 < U^* < 6$, what leads to a phase shift to 180° within such range. Altogether, this picture helps understanding the dynamic response identified in Fig. 3(a1) for $l^* = 1$ and 3 configurations, whereby the system has an enhanced vibration at low U^* (especially for the shortest plate) and attenuated vibrations over the upper and lower branches, although monotonously growing with U^* . The growing excitation with the reduced velocity is expected to lead to amplified responses beyond the upper limit of U^* studied here.

On the other hand, for the plate of $l^* = 2$ the lift and associated components show an intermediate behavior between $l^* = 1$ and 3. In particular, lift components feature maxima at lowest values of reduced velocity and decreasing amplitudes as reduced velocity grows, to reach nearly nil magnitudes for $U^* > 5$. The absence of excitation of the flow acting on the structure above $U^* = 5$ coincides with the mitigated dynamic response of the system observed in Fig. 3(a1). That said, the plate of $l^* = 2$ behaves therefore as an excellent configuration in terms of excitation, as shorter and longer plates present magnified coefficients. This better performance of the $l^* = 2$ plate may be linked to the fact that the typical vortex formation length observed for these kind of flows is around $2D$, as seen in Sect. IV. Therefore, that plate's length mitigates the interaction between shear layers, reducing the flow excitation to the system.

FIG. 14. Amplitude of (a) lift coefficient, \hat{C}_y , along with corresponding components in phase with velocity (b) and displacement (c), and phase difference between lift and y -displacement (d), for different values of stiffness $k_p = [k_{p1}, k_{p2}, k_{p3}, k_{p4}] = [0.034, 0.096, 0.598, \rightarrow \infty]$ N·m/rad and plate length $l^* = 2$. A solid line has been included for $\hat{C}_{y,a}$ to illustrate the effective added mass and phase between forcing and response.

The effect of the hinge torsional stiffness k_p on the lift coefficient and components is next analyzed with help of Fig. 14, where results for arrangements with $l^* = 2$ are plotted. Such variable may help estimating the capacity of adaptation of the plate to the motion of the cylinder and wake forcing. As already identified in the amplitude response for the different joints in Fig. 5, there are two distinct regions of dynamic response, at low ($U^* < 5.5$) and high ($U^* > 7$) reduced velocity respectively, which are also distinguishable for the lift coefficient in Fig. 14(a), although there are important differences between trends of

568 different k_p . In particular, it is observed that, as the torsional stiffness increases, so does
 569 the value of the lift amplitude \hat{C}_y at low values of the reduced velocity, being the rigid
 570 joint, i.e. k_{p4} , the case of largest excitation within the range of $3.8 \geq U^* < 5.5$, where
 571 $\hat{C}_y \simeq 2$. The excitation of the cylinder-plate system is considerably weakened between
 572 $5 < U^* < 7$, as the lift amplitude decreases abruptly, coincident with the attenuation of
 573 oscillations over the original upper branch of the plain cylinder and beginning of the lower
 574 branch. Moreover, following the vortex shedding sequences shown in Figs. 10 and 11, for
 575 different stiffness values, corresponding to k_{p2} and k_{p4} plates respectively, just at $U^* = 5.3$,
 576 a general behaviour can be inferred depending on the stiffness value. It appears that the
 577 flow topology is similar for both cases, however, while for the extreme case corresponding to
 578 a rigid plate, k_{p4} , the wake excitation has to be directly absorbed by the cylinder (and thus
 579 by the springs on the low mass-damping system), in the case of the more-flexibly-hinged
 580 plates the effect of the wake excitation is divided between the cylinder and the flexible
 581 hinge, which reduces the response of the whole system. Finally, the lift amplitude grows
 582 again at higher U^* , for all values of k_p , except for k_{p2} , for which the excitation is nearly
 583 nil, $\hat{C}_y \simeq 0$. In particular, the values of \hat{C}_y of k_{p1} and k_{p3} are similar to that of the plain
 584 cylinder, whereas that of the static plate rises monotonously to reach large amplitudes of
 585 $\hat{C}_y \simeq 1$.

586 In spite of the large amplitudes of the lift coefficient displayed by the cylinder-plate
 587 arrangements for low and high ranges of reduced velocity, it was shown that the amplitude
 588 response is however attenuated with respect to that of the plain cylinder. That effect may
 589 be caused by the low stiffness of the flexible hinge and to the reduced wake transversal
 590 velocity induced by the hinged plates. Moreover, the component $\hat{C}_{y,u}$ is in general very
 591 small, and smaller than that of the reference case, as expected from an attenuated response
 592 and weak energy transfer from the fluid to the cylinder-plate system. In particular, the
 593 highest values of $\hat{C}_{y,u}$ of the controlled systems are displayed by the arrangement with the
 594 most flexible joint, k_{p1} , and rigid case k_{p4} , for $U^* < 6$ and $7 < U^* < 9$ respectively, just
 595 where the amplitude response of these configuration is less attenuated (Fig. 5a1).

596 Additionally, the trends of component $\hat{C}_{y,a}$ are very similar to that of the lift components,
 597 displaying again amplified values over the two distinct regions at low and high reduced ve-
 598 locities, when compared to the reference cylinder case. This again can be interpreted as an
 599 increase of the added mass, and lower response frequencies, as observed in Fig. 5. Inter-
 600 estingly, for k_{p1} , $\hat{C}_{y,a}$ never takes negative values, what translates into a phase difference
 601 between forcing and response of 0° , as depicted in Fig. 14(d). For the remaining cases with
 602 higher stiffness, $\hat{C}_{y,a}$ is only negative within an interval covering a $6 < U^* < 7.5$ approxi-
 603 mately, and therefore, the shift in the phase difference from 0° to 180° is soon reverted for
 604 $U^* > 7.5$, from where the forcing and response are back in phase. As discussed earlier, the
 605 first shift has been generally identified as one of the characteristics of lock-in in VIV of a
 606 plain cylinder¹³, whereas the subsequent drop to small values of Φ are an indication of the
 607 beginning of galloping-like responses¹⁵.

608 B. Spectral analysis of the cross-flow forcing

609 In general, in view of the previous results, two types of responses have been identified for
 610 the cylinder-plate assemblies. In particular, depending on the plate's length and torsional
 611 stiffness of the joint, a VIV regime featuring small-amplitude oscillation may develop at
 612 low values of U^* , over the initial branch of response; while galloping-like responses can be
 613 triggered at high U^* .

614 Following the latter observation, we will next discuss these different regimes in terms of
 615 the forcing frequency, provided by the spectral analysis of the lift coefficient, c_y . Thus,
 616 Fig. 15 displays PSD spectra from cross-flow force signals along with their corresponding
 617 dominant forcing and oscillation frequencies, for the plain cylinder case (Fig. 15a) and
 618 controlled configurations of different lengths (Fig. 15, b-d) and torsional stiffness (Fig. 15
 619

FIG. 15. PSD spectra of cross-flow force signals, c_y depicted by background contours and corresponding dominant forcing frequency (white triangle symbols) and response oscillation frequency (black circles) for plain cylinder (a, top row) and controlled configurations: with plates of length (medium row) $l^* = 1$ (b), 2 (c) and 3 (d), for intermediate value of the torsional stiffness k_{p2} ; with torsional stiffness (bottom row) k_{p1} (e), k_{p3} (f) and k_{p4} (g), for a fixed plate of length $l^* = 2$. Dashed lines represent the Strouhal law with $St \simeq 0.18$, the colormap indicates value of PSD amplitude of cross-flow force and the solid line is $f^* = 1$.

620 c,e-g). Power spectra are used here to qualitatively estimate the intensity of wake oscillations
 621 and coherence of vortex shedding. In general, the response frequency is coincident with
 622 the dominant forcing frequency for the whole range of reduced velocity investigated and
 623 different configurations, showing a strong coupling as the flow and the solid dynamics are
 624 highly synchronized.

625 The plain cylinder case is characterized by three intervals of forcing. Thus, the initial
 626 branch displays frequencies that follow approximately the Strouhal law, until a point where
 627 the oscillations in the wake attain its largest magnitude, from which frequencies start to
 628 level off, with $f^* = 1$ thus marking the beginning of the upper branch. For $U^* \simeq 6$,
 629 the magnitude of PSD decreases, a known feature of the transition region between upper
 630 and lower branches³⁰. From here on, the dominant frequencies reach a plateau at $f^* \geq 1$
 631 (as it typically occurs for flexibly mounted cylinders with low mass ratios). At the lower
 632 branch, the magnitude of PSD decreases and more periodic spectra with thinner peaks are
 633 observed³⁰.

634 The effect of installing a flexibly-hinged plate is evident in terms of frequency forcing and
 635 spectral amplitude, as observed in Fig. 15(b-g). Let us begin the discussion on the effect of
 636 the increasing torsional stiffness k_p for a constant plate's length. In particular, as observed
 637 in Fig. 15(e) for the most flexible joint of k_{p1} , the excitation is guided by an increasing
 638 frequency which follows approximately a linear trend, until reaching the value of $f^* = 1$,

639 from which the spectral amplitude becomes nearly indiscernible, and the frequency decreases
 640 below $f^* = 1$, although its value remains close to it. As detailed in Sahu, Furquan, and
 641 Mittal²⁰ and observed in our PIV measurements, the frequency of the shedding guiding the
 642 VIV regime decreases with the addition of plates, as so does the spacing between the vortices
 643 when compared to the original cylinder wake. Besides, the drop in frequency at $U^* = 9.0$,
 644 is shown to be associated to a discontinuity or *kink* in the trend of amplitude response in
 645 Fig. 5(a1), similar to that reported, e.g. by Bearman *et al.*³³ for squared cylinders. This
 646 behavior is generally attributed to interaction between VIV and galloping-like responses.
 647 In fact, as shown in Fig. 14(d), no change in phase difference is observed and $\Phi = 0^\circ$ over
 648 the whole range of U^* studied here.

649 As the stiffness of the joint increases, the range of reduced velocity for which the VIV
 650 regime (resp. galloping-like) is active narrows (resp. widens) progressively, as it can be
 651 inferred from Fig. 15(c), (f) and (g), which represent respectively k_{p2} , k_{p3} and k_{p4} . Interest-
 652 ingly, the forcing frequency features are very similar for the three values of stiffness, with
 653 the transition between VIV and galloping-like regimes being set around $U^* = 7.0$. This
 654 transition between regimes is clearly identified in the phase difference diagram of Fig. 14(d)
 655 with corresponding shifts from 180° to 0° , and occurs when the vibration frequency crosses
 656 the natural frequency of the system³⁴. There are however notable differences in terms of
 657 spectral amplitude, i.e. excitation magnitude. Thus, excepting for the preferred case of k_{p2}
 658 for which the vibrations are mitigated and no coherence is found for the forcing frequency at
 659 high U^* , it is seen that increasing the stiffness beyond such a best-performing value of k_{p2} ,
 660 rises the cross-flow force energy over both VIV and galloping-like regimes, being it maxi-
 661 mum for the rigid static plate. This is in line with Fig. 12, the k_{p4} case, the integral wake
 662 transversal velocity is higher than in the k_{p2} case, which may indicate a greater excitement
 663 in the wake, possibly justifying the higher response of the cylinder.

664 On the other hand, the effect of varying the plate length while keeping constant the stiff-
 665 ness, i.e. k_{p2} , may produce similar excitation to that provided by the increasing stiffness,
 666 as illustrated in Fig. 15(b,d), where both VIV and galloping-like regimes are clearly distin-
 667 guishable, as in Fig. 15 (g). In particular, the shortest plate $l^* = 1$ displays intense spectral
 668 amplitude along the initial branch, which excites the system close to the natural frequency,
 669 thus leading to amplified vibrations along the initial branch in Fig. 3(a1). When the forcing
 670 frequency reaches the value of $f^* \simeq 1$, there is a transition towards the galloping-like regime,
 671 characterized by a constant and low forcing frequency and strong spectral magnitude. The
 672 dynamic behaviour is very similar to that of the static $l^* = 1$ plate analyzed in Assi and
 673 Bearman¹³, and it might be attributed to the fact that the plate lies inside the vortex
 674 formation length (see Figs. 8, 9), therefore it is weakly excited by the shedding.

675 When the plate's length is increased to $l^* = 3$, above the more suitable case of $l^* = 2$, the
 676 VIV regime at low reduced velocity is less intense and extends now up to $U^* \simeq 6.0$. From
 677 here, the new regime at high U^* displays again a forcing frequency $f^* < 1$ which increases
 678 now slightly with U^* , with a slope that is approximately $0.5St \cdot U^*$. This slowdown of
 679 the forcing with some degree of synchronization with the behavior of the Strouhal law, is
 680 presumably consequence of the strong flapping process (see Fig. 3b1) which now guides the
 681 shedding.

682 C. Drag coefficient

683 Finally, we will evaluate the effect of control plates on the mean drag coefficient, C_x .
 684 Figure 16 displays the time-averaged drag coefficient C_x as a function of the reduced velocity
 685 for controlled systems with different plate's length l^* for a constant stiffness k_{p2} (a) and
 686 different torsional stiffness k_p for a constant $l^* = 2$ (b), along with the plain cylinder case,
 687 which is shown for comparison. In general, for the uncontrolled case, the drag coefficient
 688 is sensitive to the branches of the amplitude response (see Figs. 3 and 5) displaying larger
 689 values along the upper branch, where the response is highest, and showing lower values at
 690 initial and lower branches, where the value is similar to those typically reported for static

691 cylinders, at the same Re .

FIG. 16. Time-averaged drag coefficient for different k_p configurations of the cylinder and plate system: (a) effect of the plate's length l^* for constant k_{p2} and (b) effect of the torsional stiffness of the joint k_p for a constant $l^* = 2$.

692 In general, the addition of a rear plate reduces dramatically the magnitude of the mean
 693 drag, which now displays nearly constant values for all configurations between 0.9 and 1.
 694 In order to identify the relationship between the measured force coefficient and the near
 695 wake features, time averaged flow fields for the fixed cylinder case and a cylinder-plate
 696 arrangement (l_2^* , k_{p2}) at $U^* = 5.3$ ($Re \simeq 7000$) are depicted in Fig. 17. It can be noticed
 697 that the presence of the plate is seen to separate the two recirculating cores of the near wake
 698 and to induce the elongation of the recirculation region, giving rise to the drag reduction as
 699 a consequence of the strong streamlining of the wake, as pointed out by Apelt, West, and
 700 Szewczyk¹².

701 Thus, it is seen that, in general, increasing the length of the plate (Fig. 16a) translates
 702 into slight reductions of C_x within the range of U^* studied herein. Some small differences
 703 associated to the dynamic behavior of the system are however discernible. For instance,
 704 at low U^* the drag of the arrangement with $l^* = 1$ increases on account of the amplified
 705 response of the system, mainly due to the widening of the wake transverse extension induced
 706 by the presence of a rear plate. This fact can be observed in the comparison of the average
 707 velocity contours shown in Fig. 17. Such an effect may become important for conditions
 708 of low values of U^* and small l^* , under which the shear effect due to the stream, barely
 709 elongates the recirculation region, being l^* not long enough to maintain the flow attachment.
 710 Similarly, the amplified oscillations of the system with $l^* = 3$ for high values of U^* increases
 711 somewhat the mean drag above that of $l^* = 2$.

712 Regarding the effect of the torsional stiffness k_p , little differences are found among the
 713 cases, if only, the static plate provides with lower values of drag, on account of the nonex-
 714 istent flapping of plates, which has been shown to decrease the pressure in the near wake of
 715 bluff bodies³⁵ and to increase the velocity magnitude inside the recirculation region. Lastly,
 716 it is interesting to note that, the stable steady deflection of the plate with k_{p1} for $U^* > 9.0$
 717 translates into a very slight reduction of the mean drag.

718 VI. CONCLUSIONS

719 We have experimentally analyzed the flow-induced vibrations of a circular cylinder controlled
 720 with a flexibly-hinged splitter plate subject to uniform cross-flow. In particular,
 721 two parametric studies are included in order to characterize the effect of the control device
 722 with respect to the isolated plain cylinder case. First, three different lengths have been
 723 tested, namely $l^* = L_p/D = [1, 2, 3]$, for a given torsional stiffness of the joint k_p . Second,

FIG. 17. Time averaged velocity magnitude contours along with flow streamlines for (a) fixed plain cylinder case and (b) k_{p2} cylinder-plate arrangement of $l^* = 2$ at $U^* = 5.3$ ($Re \simeq 7000$).

724 keeping constant the length of the plate to $l^* = 2$, four different values of the torsional
 725 stiffness are tested $k_p = [0.034, 0.096, 0.598, \infty)$ N · m/rad, where $k_p \rightarrow \infty$ represents the
 726 rigid case. In general, it is found that the introduction of the hinged plate can suppress
 727 the cylinder vibration and reduce the drag force at low and medium U^* . For high values of
 728 the reduced velocity, beyond the range herein investigated, the plain cylinder can perform
 729 better as galloping-type responses are reported when the plates are installed. Reductions
 730 of the dynamic response of more than 90% can be generally reached at the upper branch,
 731 especially when a plate of $l^* = 2$ with intermediate degree of torsional stiffness is attached,
 732 which is shown to represent the most effective solution as it mitigates the oscillations of the
 733 system for the whole range of U^* investigated.

734 More specifically, variations on the lengths and stiffness of the joint are associated to
 735 different coupled dynamics of the system and different near wake topologies. The dynamic
 736 responses of the different arrangements of cylinder and hinged plate are not alike that of the
 737 plain cylinder (characterized by the classical initial, upper and lower branches), and show
 738 two distinct regimes, whereby the dynamics at low values of reduced velocity are character-
 739 ized by a modified VIV response, whereas for high values of U^* the dynamics feature
 740 galloping-like responses. In general, the response is shown to be strongly synchronized with
 741 the cross-flow forcing dynamics, especially in terms of characteristic frequencies. Thus, the
 742 VIV responses are in any case attenuated and show mild oscillations guided by an increasing
 743 shedding frequency, until the ratio $f^* > 1$, for which a general transition to galloping-like
 744 dynamics, characterized by $f^* < 1$ occurs. Transition between regimes are associated to
 745 shifts in the phase difference between the forcing and response, which typically retrieves
 746 the value of 0° when the galloping dynamics establishes.

747 The roles of the torsional stiffness of the joint and length are key, as demonstrated by
 748 the large attenuation provided by $l^* = 2$ and intermediate value of k_p . In particular, it
 749 has been inferred from the flow measurements that, such a length value lies around the
 750 vortex formation length typically observed for the tested Re range. This fact together with
 751 the ability of the plate to mildly adapt to flow changes lead to a reduction of the system
 752 excitation through the inhibition of the interaction between the shear layers developed in
 753 both sides of the cylinder.

754 Thus, using the same length, it has been shown that stiffer joints may promote the
 755 emergence of galloping-like responses for high values of the reduced velocity, thus mimicking
 756 the response of rigid plates^{15,20}. Conversely, a more flexible joint (lower value of k_p) extends
 757 the prevalence of an attenuated VIV response to high U^* , and postpone the emergence of
 758 a galloping like-response.

759 The previous scenario can be affected by the change of the plate length. Thus, it is seen
 760 that the shortest plate of $l^* = 1$ excites the synchronization VIV response at low values of
 761 U^* , and behaves like a static plate, while it may promote unstable oscillations of the system

at high U^* , behaving in a similar manner to a static plate²⁷. In fact, this plate length lies inside the measured recirculating bubble behind the cylinder, and therefore is less exposed to changes in pressure given by the shedding, thus reducing its capability to adapt passively its position to flow changes. Conversely, the longest plate of $l^* = 3$, is clearly subject to enhanced oscillations at high U^* (where the nondimensional flexibility of the system increases), due to its larger surface and stronger interference with the wake, what promotes a progressive amplification of the response of the system at high U^* . Interestingly, although the oscillating dynamics is characterized by a frequency ratio $f^* < 1$, the frequency is seen to increase linearly with U^* , as if the dynamics is guided by the slower shedding provoked by the flapping.

Besides, it has been shown that, a certain level of torsional stiffness is required to correct potential asymmetric mean positions of the hinged plate. In particular, this departure from the symmetric location has been only observed for the most flexible case of $k_{p1} = 0.034 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}/\text{rad}$. This stable departure from the centred location is reminiscent from the steady bifurcation reported by Cimbala and Garg²¹ and Gu *et al.*²⁴ for rotary plates around the static cylinder, and the elastically-mounted cylinder²⁵. The steady mode is shown therein to reduce the excitation of the system, which has been also confirmed here.

Finally, when compared to flexible plates¹⁸ or rigid plates¹⁵, as control devices for VIV, the hinged plates display intermediate behavior between these two configurations, where the complete suppression of VIV or the excitation of galloping-like responses can be either promoted, depending on the capacity to adapt to flow changes that is given by the plate length and torsional stiffness. In all plate cases, the shear layers are seen to wrap around the plate alternatively. However, while for the rigid plate, k_{p4} , the wake excitation has to go directly to the cylinder (and to the springs on the low mass-damping system), in the case of the flexibly-hinged plates, the wake excitation is divided between the cylinder and the silicone rubber.

In summary, the use of hinged plates has been proven to provide with a significant attenuation of the VIV amplitude and drag reductions, a feature that can be considered of practical relevance in many engineering applications. The selection of parameters, such a torsional stiffness and plate length is however a key aspect to promote different controlled dynamic responses, whereby the excitation can lead to galloping-like responses in some cases. The obtained results allow to perform a more detailed study where additional plate's lengths can be tested. Moreover, a deeper analysis on the fluid-structure mechanism behind the forcing transfer between the flow and the cylinder-plate system can be addressed. Finally, a multi-body response model can be adapted to the problem in order to analyze which part of the wake excitation is sunk by the flexible hinge or by the system's springs. These features can be also of interest for practical systems where energy harvesting is envisaged.

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